

NOTCH SENSITIVITY OF ARALL®¹ LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

An experimental study on the notch sensitivity of three different types of ARALL laminates was conducted. ARALL laminates are hybrid composites consisting of alternating layers of aluminum and unidirectional aramid/epoxy. The three laminates differ in that different aluminum alloys and manufacturing steps are utilized. Notched ARALL 1, ARALL 2 and ARALL 1X laminate coupons were tested and the effects of fiber orientation, notch geometry and notch size were considered. For this study, two fiber orientations (0° and 90°) were considered for each laminate. Notch geometries included both center slots and center circular holes with notch-length-to-specimen-width ratios ranging from 0.063 to 0.250. The Notch Sensitivity Index (NSI) is introduced as a means to rate the relative notch effects. Results show that the specimens with slots are always more notch sensitive than those with circular holes of equivalent size and that the ARALL laminates are more notch sensitive to loading in the fiber direction than to loading transverse to the fiber. The ARALL 1 laminate exhibited the lowest notch sensitivity, whereas the ARALL 2 laminate exhibited the highest notch sensitivity.

INTRODUCTION

The ARALL laminate is a hybrid composite material, consisting of thin sheets of aluminum bonded together with a structural adhesive reinforced with aramid fibers. Developed at Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands¹, ARALL laminates are now being manufactured by Alcoa. ARALL laminates combine the excellent properties of high strength aluminum with those of fibrous composite materials. This combination results in a laminate with a lower density and superior fatigue resistance than the constituent aluminum.

The hybrid ARALL laminates also have some advantages over conventional fibrous composite systems. Resin matrix composites are susceptible to moisture absorption, which may degrade the performance of the laminate. In the ARALL laminate, the aluminum skin provides a barrier to the moisture. Likewise the aramid/epoxy layers provide a corrosion barrier between the aluminum layers. Fibrous composite materials typically have a low tolerance to impact damage, while the ARALL laminate requires a higher impact energy to cause delamination. A visual dent will generally occur in the aluminum skin prior to internal damage. ARALL laminates can be cut, drilled, sawed and milled by normal workshop procedures.

ARALL laminates clearly have several advantages over their constituent materials and are promising new materials for the aerospace industry. If the full potential of ARALL laminates, or any material, is to be realized, the effect of a notch on the material's response must be understood. This paper presents results of a study on the notch sensitivity of ARALL laminates.

aluminum sheet	(0.30 mm)
aramid/epoxy	(0.22 mm)
aluminum sheet	(0.30 mm)
aramid/epoxy	(0.22 mm)
aluminum sheet	(0.30 mm)

Fig. 1 Schematic of 3/2 ARALL laminate.

¹ARALL is a trademark of Alcoa.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

1. Materials

Three ARALL laminates were tested as part of this study, namely, the ARALL 1, ARALL 2 and ARALL 1X laminates. Each laminate was of a 3/2 configuration; three layers of aluminum bonded together by two layers of unidirectional aramid/epoxy. The ARALL laminates differ from one another in the constituent aluminum alloy and manufacturing process. ARALL 1 laminate contains aluminum alloy 7475-T6; ARALL 2 laminate contains aluminum alloy 2024-T3 and ARALL 1X laminate contains aluminum alloy 7075-T6. As part of the manufacturing process, the ARALL 1 and ARALL 1X laminates are prestrained in the fiber direction to a permanent laminate strain of 0.4%. This added step introduces a residual compressive stress in the aluminum layers which increases the yield stress of the laminate over that of the as-cured laminate. (ARALL 1X laminate refers to an early ARALL laminate that was replaced by the current ARALL 1 laminate. While no official name has been given to this laminate, for the purpose of this paper it will be referred to as ARALL 1X laminate.)

Alcoa supplied a 1.2 m by 1.2 m (4 ft by 4 ft) sheet of each of the three ARALL laminates. A band saw with a diamond impregnated blade was used to section the sheets into smaller panels of the desired fiber direction. A precision wafering machine was used to cut specimens of the appropriate width. The material characterization test coupons were 25.4 mm (1.0 in.) wide and the notch sensitivity coupons were 50.8 mm (2.0 in.) wide (Fig. 2). All specimens were 356 mm (14.0 in.) long with 50.8 mm (2.0 in.) reserved at each end for gripping, leaving a gage length of 254 mm (10.0 in.). The circular holes were manufactured using an end mill with a four fluted end mill bit. Before the slots could be made, a small hole 0.95 mm (0.037 in.) was drilled through the center of the specimen. This pilot hole allowed a diamond impregnated wire to be passed through it to manufacture the slot. The pilot hole also served as the means for mounting a small notch opening displacement gage. Notch sizes considered were 3.18 mm (1/8 in.), 6.35 mm (1/4 in.) and 12.7 mm (1/2 in.).

2. Test Procedures

Strain gages were implemented for monitoring the far field strains. A three-arm rectangular (0° - 45° - 90°) rosette was mounted on the front center-line of the specimen midway between the notch and the gripping region. A uniaxial strain gage was bonded to the back of the specimen to detect the presence of bending. A notch opening displacement gage was mounted in the circular holes to monitor the notch opening displacement (NOD). A smaller NOD gage was mounted in the pilot hole of the slotted specimens.

Fig. 2 Notched Specimen Geometry.

Fig. 3 Tensile response comparison of ARALL 2 laminate coupons.

All tests were performed using a screw-driven displacement-controlled UTS load frame. Standard Instron grips were used. The data acquisition system consisted of a Vishay 2100 Series signal conditioner/amplifier interfaced to a Data Translation DT2805/5716 in an IBM PC-XT. The data acquisition and processing software was MATPAC.² Detailed test procedures are presented in Ref. 1.

As part of the notch sensitivity study, unnotched coupons were tested to determine the in-plane laminate elastic properties, yield stress and strength of each laminate. These tests included specimens of four fiber orientations, 0° , 15° , 45° and 90° . Representative stress-strain curves of the ARALL 2 laminate are presented in Fig. 2 for the

orientations considered. It can be seen that loading in the fiber direction (0° specimen) results in bilinear behavior, due to the continued reinforcement of the laminate by the aramid/epoxy following the yielding of the aluminum. The 15° coupons also exhibit significant strain hardening. It is interesting to note that the fracture angle of the 15° ARALL laminate was such that fibers were broken across the width of the coupon, whereas the unidirectional aramid/epoxy fracture surface coincides with the fiber angle⁴. The 45° and 90° ARALL laminate coupons exhibited responses characteristic of their constituent aluminum. After yielding, these coupons exhibited no significant strain hardening prior to failure. ARALL 1 and ARALL 1X laminates behave similarly to the ARALL 2 laminate, although the use of the high yield stress 7000-series aluminum and the manufacturer's prestraining process results in higher laminate yield stresses and ultimate strengths.

NOTCH SENSITIVITY

1. Definitions

Notch sensitivity results are typically presented as a strength ratio, i.e., the strength of the notched specimen (expressed in terms of the far field ultimate stress) normalized with respect to the unnotched strength. This is a very simple technique, but it does not take into account the reduction of cross-sectional area in the notched specimens. As a result, the numerical value obtained can be somewhat misleading as to notch sensitivity. Further, the strength ratio decreases as the notch sensitivity increases, ... a most undesirable consequence.

In order to eliminate some of the confusion which may result with the use of the strength ratio, we chose to introduce a new term, the *Notch Sensitivity Index (NSI)*. NSI includes consideration of the reduced cross-sectional area and can be positive or negative with zero corresponding to a notch insensitive specimen and 1.0 corresponding to fully notch sensitive. An NSI value of 1.0 is not attainable; it can only be attained asymptotically as the notch size approaches the specimen width. The NSI is defined as

$$NSI = 1 - \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ns}}{\sigma^u} \quad (1)$$

where σ^u is the ultimate stress of the unnotched specimen and $\bar{\sigma}_{ns}$ is the average stress across the reduced net section. Rewriting this expression in terms of the far field stress at failure of the notched specimen, σ^n , and geometric parameters,

$$NSI = 1 - \left[\frac{w}{w-2c} \right] \frac{\sigma^n}{\sigma^u} \quad (2)$$

where W is the specimen width and $2c$ is the notch size perpendicular to the loading direction.

Fig. 4 Strength ratio comparison, 0° ARALL laminate, center slot.

Fig. 5 Strength ratio comparison, 90° ARALL laminate, center hole.

2. Results

Experimental results are presented in Table 1 and Figs. 4-8. The table includes the far field failure stress and NSI values for all three materials, fiber orientations and notch geometries. The values represent the average for three replicates of each test.

Typical results for the normalized notched strength of coupons with slots in specimens with the fiber in the 0° (loading) direction are presented in Fig. 4 for all three ARALL laminates. As expected, the notched strength decreases with an increase in notch size. The solid line in Fig. 4 corresponds the average failure stress in the net section being equal to the ultimate strength of the unnotched laminate. This figure indicates that the notched behavior is very similar for all three laminates with ARALL 2 being the most notch sensitive and ARALL 1 the least notch sensitive. For the largest notch size, the notched strength of all three materials has decreased approximately 50%.

Typical normalized notched strength results for specimens with the fibers oriented perpendicular to the loading direction and with center holes are presented in Fig. 5. It is apparent that these specimens are less notch sensitive than the 0° specimens but otherwise follow the same trend. Notched strength decreases with an increase in notch size. All three materials behave very similarly and ARALL 1 is the least notch sensitive; ARALL 2 is the most notch

Table 1. Notched Strength of ARALL Laminates

Material	Fiber Orientation	Notch Size mm (in.)	Notch Type			
			Center Hole		Center Slot	
			Strength MPa (ksi)	NSI	Strength MPa (ksi)	NSI
ARALL® 1	0°	unnotched	779 (113)	0.00	779 (113)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	554 (80.4)	0.24	547 (79.3)	0.25
		6.35 (0.250)	497 (72.1)	0.27	467 (67.8)	0.32
		12.7 (0.500)	407 (59.0)	0.30	362 (52.5)	0.38
ARALL® 1	90°	unnotched	390 (56.6)	0.00	390 (56.6)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	351 (50.9)	0.04	329 (47.7)	0.10
		6.35 (0.250)	324 (47.0)	0.05	290 (42.1)	0.15
		12.7 (0.500)	285 (41.4)	0.03	240 (34.8)	0.18
ARALL® 2	0°	unnotched	685 (99.3)	0.00	685 (99.3)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	451 (65.4)	0.30	430 (62.3)	0.33
		6.35 (0.250)	391 (56.7)	0.35	359 (52.0)	0.40
		12.7 (0.500)	328 (47.5)	0.36	293 (42.5)	0.43
ARALL® 2	90°	unnotched	319 (46.2)	0.00	319 (46.2)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	257 (37.3)	0.14	234 (34.0)	0.22
		6.35 (0.250)	245 (35.5)	0.12	214 (31.0)	0.23
		12.7 (0.500)	218 (31.6)	0.09	180 (26.1)	0.25
ARALL® 1X	0°	unnotched	827 (120)	0.00	827 (120)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	563 (81.7)	0.27	559 (81.1)	0.28
		6.35 (0.250)	501 (72.7)	0.31	470 (68.2)	0.35
		12.7 (0.500)	417 (60.5)	0.33	363 (52.6)	0.41
ARALL® 1X	90°	unnotched	392 (56.8)	0.00	392 (56.8)	0.00
		3.18 (0.125)	342 (49.6)	0.07	315 (45.7)	0.14
		6.35 (0.250)	322 (46.7)	0.06	278 (40.3)	0.19
		12.7 (0.500)	280 (40.6)	0.05	225 (32.7)	0.23

sensitive. The largest decrease in notched strength is only 32% compared to the 56% reduction for the cases presented in Fig. 4. It may be apparent to the discerning eye that the *notch sensitivity* initially increases and then decreases with increasing notch size for this case of circular holes and loading transverse to the fibers.

The Notch Sensitivity Index (NSI) values for the two configurations presented in Figs. 4 and 5 are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. The *sensitivity* of the notches is very evident in these figures. For the 0° coupons with slots, NSI increases with increasing notch size, but appears to be approaching a limiting value. The maximum NSI is 0.36. All three materials exhibit similar characteristics and ARALL 2 is the most notch sensitive and ARALL 1 is the least notch sensitive as previously noted.

Fig. 6 Notch Sensitivity Index comparison, 0° ARALL laminate, circular slot.

Fig. 7 Notch Sensitivity Index comparison, 90° ARALL laminate, center hole.

Fig. 8 Notch Sensitivity comparison, three ARALL laminates.

The NSI results for the 90° coupons with holes (Fig. 7) are in stark contrast to those for the slotted 0° coupons in Fig. 6. For the case of a circular hole in a 90° coupon, NSI increases for small hole sizes and then decreases thereafter. This response is very similar for all three ARALL laminates, and as indicated previously, ARALL 2 is the most notch sensitive and ARALL 1 is the least notch sensitive. Interestingly, for large notch sizes, NSI approaches zero for this case of a circular hole in a 90° coupon. This may be an indication that the aluminum has yielded across the entire width of the notched specimen in the vicinity of the net reduced cross section.

Fig. 8 presents a summary of notch sensitivity results for each individual ARALL laminate investigated. Each figure presents NSI values as a function of notch size for both fiber direction and notch types. It is evident from these figures that a slot in a 0° coupon is always the most notch sensitive and that a hole in a 90° coupon is the least notch sensitive. 0° coupons are always more notch sensitive than 90° coupons for all three types of ARALL laminate, independent of notch type. Slotted coupons are more notch sensitive than coupons with circular holes for a specified fiber orientation. NSI values range from 0.03 for a 90° ARALL 1 laminate coupon to 0.43 for a 12.7 mm slot in a 0° ARALL 2 laminate. It is interesting to note that the largest and smallest notch sensitivities both occur for the largest notch size considered.

3. Failure Modes

The failure of each of the notched coupons was essentially the same; failure originated near the notch radius and propagated across the width of the specimen in the direction perpendicular to the load. Audible events, believed to be associated with fiber breakage, were recorded during the testing of the 0° coupons. Macroscopic examination of the fracture surface revealed fiber breakage in the aramid/epoxy layer across the width of the notched 0° coupon. This differs from the notched 0° aramid/epoxy coupon which exhibited fiber-matrix separation starting at the notch radius and extending toward the grip region parallel to the load direction.⁴ Thus the failure mode of the aramid/epoxy plies in the notched 0° ARALL laminate is significantly different than that of the notched 0° aramid/epoxy coupon. In contrast, crack growth in 90° ARALL laminate coupons, which followed the same geometric path as the 0° ARALL laminate coupons, propagated parallel to the fibers and was devoid of fiber breakage.

SUMMARY

Center notched tensile coupons were tested to investigate the notch sensitivity of ARALL 1, ARALL 2 and ARALL 1X laminates. 0° and 90° coupons were tested to provide results for loading in the fiber direction and the transverse direction, respectively. The notch types considered were slots and circular holes; the notch sizes ranged from 3.18mm (0.125 in.) to 12.7mm (0.500 in.) in 50.8 mm (2.00 in.) specimens. The Notch Sensitivity Index was introduced as means of quantifying the notched strength. Based upon the test results the following conclusions can be made.

In general, the ARALL 2 laminate is the most notch sensitive and the ARALL 1 laminate is the least notch sensitive for all coupons tested. For the notched coupons, the maximum NSI value was 0.43 (0° ARALL 2 coupon with 12.7mm slot), while the minimum value was 0.03 (90° ARALL 1 coupon with 12.7 mm hole).

For all three ARALL laminates, the 0° coupons exhibited a higher notch sensitivity than the 90° coupons, and the coupons with slots were always more notch sensitive than those with circular holes of the same notch size.

The notch sensitivity index increased with increasing notch size for all cases except the 90° coupons with holes. For this case, the notch sensitivity index attains a maximum value for a relatively small hole size and then decreases for larger holes.

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